

MOLECULAR PHYSIOLOGY AND GENETICS

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF MATERIALS FOR ROOT CANAL FILLING

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Abstract

The most important issue in practical endodontics is the correct choice of materials for obturation of the root canal. The completion of endodontic treatment consists of complete and permanent closure of the root canal with a biocompatible material that is impenetrable to bacteria.

Keywords: Obturation of root canals, dye permeability.

However, there is still no answer to the question of what materials are considered optimal for root canal filling. The basic principles of root canal treatment were formulated more than 100 years ago. In 1913, Albrecht proposed a method for filling root canals, which was later called "resorcinol-formalin." Since the 70s, hardening pastes have been widely used for filling root canals. However, the fact that the paste can shrink in volume when it hardens at the tooth root (shrinkage of the material) and dissolve upon contact with tissue fluid is its disadvantage [1, 2]. In the process of continuous search for new methods and materials for filling root canals, gutta-percha was proposed, which became the most popular material for filling root canals. Currently, a large number of endosealants have been obtained for filling root canals, and the doctor's ability to make the right choice of the drug and filling method is one of the most important conditions for effective endodontic treatment. There are many different techniques for filling root canals using gutta-percha [3,4]. The most commonly used method in our country is the lateral condensation method and the single pin method. The purpose of the study was to determine the permeability of the dye into the root canal filled with the methods of one paste, lateral condensation, one pin using different groups of sealers. To determine apical leakage, the following groups of sealers were used: "Endomethason" (Septatont); "AH-Plus" (Densplay); "Sealapex" (Kerr); "Endion" (Voco); "Endosil" is a glass ionomer cement based on calcium phosphate ceramics produced in the Republic of Belarus. Apical penetration was determined by measuring the depth of penetration of dyes through the apical foramen into the filled root canal. The studies were carried out on the removed first central incisors of the upper jaw with a root length of 15 ± 0.5 mm. After mechanical medicinal treatment (2.5–3% sodium hypochloride and 17% EDTA solution were used as endolubricants) and subsequent drying with paper pins, the root canals were filled using the methods of one paste, lateral condensation and one pin using conical gutta-percha. The filled teeth were placed in a thermostat chamber and kept for 72 hours at a

temperature of 37 ± 1 °C and 95% humidity. After polymerization of the filling material, the roots of the teeth, except the apexes, were covered with varnish and molten wax and placed in a vertical position in a vessel with dye to the level of the coronal part for 168 hours. A 0.5% aqueous solution of fuchsin and a 2% aqueous solution of methylene blue were used as dyes. In laboratory conditions, longitudinal cuts of the teeth were carried out and sections of the samples were made on a Struers grinding machine (LaboForse, Denmark), which were examined using an optical microscope (Polivar at 40 and 80).

At least 5 samples were studied for each filling material. On sections of teeth, the canals of which were filled with the test pastes "Endomethason", "Sealapex", "AN-Plus" and cements "Unifas", "Endion", "Endosil" using the same paste method, dye penetration to different depths was observed in all samples. Dye permeability was detected in the structure of the filling material, at the border of dentin and sealer, as well as in the branch of the macrochannel. The smallest penetration depth of the dye was observed with the sealers "ANPlus" and "Endosil", the greatest - in the canals filled with pastes "Sealapex", "Endomethason" and "Unifas". The calculated level of reliability of the results is $P = 0.05$; $t = 4.3$. The second aspect of the study was to examine the apical percolation of root sealers in combination with gutta-percha points. At this stage, canal filling was carried out using the lateral condensation method and the single-pin method using conical gutta-percha. Data from the analysis of the manufactured samples showed a complete absence of dye in the canals of all groups of teeth. Penetration of the dye was detected to the level of the gutta-percha pin (1.5 - 2 mm from the anatomical apex of the tooth root), which confirmed its good ability to penetrate

Conclusions:

the most resistant (stable) to dye penetration when filling root canals using the one-paste method are endosealants "AH-Plus" and "Endosil", the least resistant are "Sealapex", "Endomethason", "Unifas"; - the use of a single pin method using conical gutta-percha allows you to reliably obturate the root canal and

use it as an alternative to filling root canals using the lateral condensation method.

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